

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Significance of Darcy Forchheimer Effect and MHD Stagnation Characteristics of Casson Ternary Nanofluid Flow Over Porous Curved Stretching Surface

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 11/02/2025

Accepted: 11/05/2025

Published: 13/07/2025

S Kumari^{1*}, S Sharma², S Prasad³, S Chandel⁴¹ Research scholar, Mathematics and statistics, Career Point University, Hamirpur, India² Assistant professor, Department of BCA & PGDCA, Govt. college Bilaspur, India³ Research scholar, Mathematics and statistics, Career Point University, Hamirpur India⁴ Assistant professor, Mathematics and statistics, Career Point University, Hamirpur, India

Citation: Kumari S, Sharma S, Prasad S, Chandel S (2025) Significance of Darcy Forchheimer Effect and MHD Stagnation Characteristics of Casson Ternary Nanofluid Flow Over Porous Curved Stretching Surface. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 18(27): 2185-2197. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v18i27.251>

* Corresponding author.

sumanjya97@gmail.com

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2025 Kumari et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.isee.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Abstract

Objective: To model and scrutinize the Darcy-Forchheimer flow with MHD stagnation characteristics of Casson ternary nanofluid flow over porous curved stretching surface. **Methods:** Flow of porous space is characterized by Darcy Forchheimer relation. Nanoparticles such as TiO_2 , MgO, and $CoFe_2O_4$ with a base fluid are investigated. The partial differential equations are reduced to ordinary differential equations through the application of a suitable similarity transformation. Numerical results for the problem are generated using the BVP4C method. The investigating the influence of different value of magnetic field parameter M, porosity parameter A, Prandtl number Pr, Darcy Forchheimer Fr, Casson fluid parameter β , nanoparticles volume fraction ϕ_1 are determined numerically and presented through graphs. The effect of various parameters on Skin friction and Nusselt number are compared and analyzed. **Findings:** Graphical representations of velocity and temperature distributions reveal the influence of emerging flow variables. In temperature profile $\theta(\eta)$ boosts for higher values of ϕ_1 , M, Fr, β . Velocity distributions $f'(\eta)$ rises for increasing values of ϕ_1 and while declines for Fr, M and β . In case of skin friction $C_{fs}(Re_s)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ shows decreasing behavior for S and λ whereas Nusselt number $Nu_s(Re_s)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ increases behavior for S and λ . **Novelty:** Given the widespread relevance and possibilities associated with non-Newtonian fluids, our study examines the present fluid problem by employing the Casson ternary nanofluid flow over porous curved stretching surface, taking into account the Darcy-Forchheimer term in momentum equation. The (MgO), (TiO_2), ($CoFe_2O_4$) study examines the flow behavior of ternary nanofluid past a curved stretching surface is considered in the present study. While no one has considered these nanofluids for the same model.

Keywords: Curved surface; Stagnation point flow; Ternary Nanofluids; Darcy-Forchheimer flow; MHD; Casson fluid

1 Introduction

During past years, flows over stretching surfaces have gained the continuous attention of scholars and researchers due to its endless applications confronted in coating industries, performance of lubricants and paints, polymer extrusion, textiles industries, glass fiber production, hot rolling, drawing of plastic, polymer and rubber sheets, manufacturing processes of artificial films and wires, locomotion of biological liquids, paper industries and so on. Dinesh et al.⁽¹⁾ focused on the MHD boundary layer flow of nanofluids over an exponentially stretching sheet, taking into account the effects of Darcy- Forchheimer flow. Despite its practical significance, the flow of viscous fluids around curved surface has been relatively unexplored in the scientific literature. Kavita et al.⁽²⁾ examined the importance of Darcy–Forchheimer Casson fluid flow over a non-permeable curved stretching sheet, with particular emphasis on heat and mass transfer phenomena. Abaas et al.⁽³⁾ exploring radiative chemical species dynamics in non-Newtonian fluids over exponentially curved stretching surfaces. Vidhya et al.⁽⁴⁾ focused on the numerical exploration of micropolar fluid stratified flow over curved stretching sheet under buoyancy effect. Nagaraja et al.⁽⁵⁾ conducted a comparative study of various numerical methods to analyze the flow characteristics over a curved surface. Pardeep et al.⁽⁶⁾ study the optimization design based on Taguchi method and statistical analysis of variance for thermo-diffusive flow over a curved sheet: entropy analysis. Nanofluids have emerged as a versatile technology with a wide range of applications, including medical software, biomedical industries, detergents, nuclear power generation, and various thermal management systems. The latest developments in nanofluid research have focused on designing hybrid nanofluids by integrate nanoparticles from three distinct materials into a base fluid. This novel nanofluid configuration is related to as ternary hybrid nanofluid, tri- hybrid nanofluid, or simply hybrid nanofluid with modified properties. Ternary Nano fluids typically consist of three components: a base fluid usually a naturally occurring liquid, metallic or non-metallic nanoparticles, and supplement to prevent nanoparticle agglomeration. Ternary nanofluid have vast potential application in various fields, including nanotechnology, bio-medical and other areas like thermal management systems such as radiators, engine cooling system, microelectronics devices like smartphones etc. Manjuntha et al.⁽⁷⁾ explored the theoretical study of convective heat transfer in ternary nanofluid flowing past a stretching sheet. The working fluid contained the titanium dioxide (TiO_2), magnesium oxide MgO, and cobalt ferrite oxide ($CoFe_2O_4$) nanoparticles in combination with water as base fluids. Titanium dioxide (TiO_2) is a skillful white inorganic compound, has been a key element in a wide range of products for over a decade. In corporation of Iron (Fe) and cobalt (Co) into metal frameworks. Fe reduces interlinear resistance, enabling enhanced surface charge mobility and a significant increase in specific capacitance. Bikram et al.⁽⁸⁾ numerically examined the influence of mixed convection and Thomson-trion slip on the flow and heat transfer characteristics of a ternary nanofluid flowing over a stretching surface in a porous medium. Moreover Arif et al.⁽⁹⁾ investigated a ternary hybrid nanofluid composed of Al_2O_3 , Grapheme, and CNT, which exhibited unique shapes. Ali and Jubair⁽¹⁰⁾ conducted a study on the rheological properties of hybrid nanofluid flow over a curved slippery surface, incorporating the effect of thermal radiation and internal heat generation. Bikram et al.⁽¹¹⁾ analyzed the preparation methods, thermophysical properties, and applications of hybrid nanofluid, highlighting their advantages and potential applications. Casson fluid flow refers to the rheological behavior of non-Newtonian fluids that obey the Casson model, which express their unique flow characteristics. This model offers a rheological description of specific non-Newtonian fluids, specifically those that display a yield stress, enabling the prediction of their flow properties. The Casson model is broadly used to investigate the flow properties of biological fluids like blood, as well as in various industrial contexts, where the impact of yield stress on fluid behavior is significant. Aljuaydi et al.⁽¹²⁾ employed artificial neural networks to numerically investigate the effects of slip and magnetic fields on the flow of Casson fluid in a porous medium, incorporating non- Fourier double diffusion principles. Almedia et al.⁽¹³⁾ study artificial neural network implementation for casson carreau nanofluid flow analysis using levenberg marquardt optimization. Mahabaleswar et al.⁽¹⁴⁾ elucidated the effect if radiation on the flow of Casson nanofluid over a stretching geometry. Additionally, Thereafter, Wang et al.⁽¹⁵⁾ expanded the theoretical framework of entropy flow of Darcy-Forchheimer flows to include the influence of viscous fluid properties. Khalil et al.⁽¹⁶⁾ study the heat transfer characteristics in thermally stratified MHD Jeffrey fluid flow over cylindrical and plane surfaces with radiation. The findings can be applied to industrial processes such as heat exchangers, cooling systems, and biomedical engineering. The study's insights on Casson ternary nanofluid flow and MHD stagnation characteristics can inform design improvements and optimization of these systems. This can lead to enhanced efficiency and performance in various industrial applications. Potential uses include advanced cooling technologies and medical device development. The motivation behind considering MHD is to analyze the interaction between electrically conducting fluids and magnetic fields. MHD effects can control fluid flow, heat transfer, and nanoparticle distribution, which are crucial in various applications, such as plasma physics, nuclear reactors, and biomedical devices. This study explores MHD's impact on Casson ternary nanofluid flow.

The primary objective of this study is to analyze the Significance of Darcy Forchheimer effect and MHD stagnation characteristics of casson ternary nanofluid flow over porous curved stretching surface. In the formulation of the Navier-Stokes

equations, the viscous term is modified to account for curvature effects. The bvp4c method is used to numerically solve the governing equations.

1.1 Flow model

The rheological equation of state used in this study for the casson fluid is adopted from the work of Vyas et al.⁽¹⁷⁾ with the assumption of isotropic and incompressible flow.

$$\tau_{ij} = \begin{cases} 2 \left(\mu_B + \frac{p_y}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \right) e_{ij}, \pi > \pi_c \\ 2 \left(\mu_B + \frac{p_y}{\sqrt{2\pi_c}} \right) e_{ij}, \pi > \pi_c \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

Where $\pi = e_{ij}e_{ij} \wedge e_{ij}$ be symptom of the deformation rate of component $(i, j)^{th}$, π is describe the product of deformation rate component with itself π_c represents the critical product value derived from non-Newtonian model, μ_B defined the plastic dynamic viscosity, a characteristic property of the non-Newtonian fluid and, p_y signifies the yield stress, a critical minimum stress required for the fluid to flow. Viscosity of casson fluid is expressed by

$$\left(\mu_B + \frac{p_y}{\sqrt{2\pi_c}} \right) e_{ij}, \pi > \pi_c, \text{ where } p_y = \frac{\nu\sqrt{2\pi}}{\beta} \tag{2}$$

and kinematic viscosity of Casson fluid is expressed as

$$\nu = \frac{\nu_B}{\rho} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) = \nu_B \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) \tag{3}$$

Where $\nu_B = \frac{\nu_B}{\rho}$ and β is Casson parameter.

2 Methodology

Fig 1. A Schematic representation of a curved stretching surface

The flow configuration model illustrated in Figure 1 involves a curved surface of radius R described by curvilinear coordinates (r, s) . At any point on the sheet, r is perpendicular to the local tangent vector and the curvilinear coordinates s represents the arc length along the flow direction, the uniform magnetic field of strength B_0 is applied perpendicular to flow direction,

the radius of curvature R is inversely related to the curvature, such that increasing values of R correspond to decreasing curvature; as noted by Sajid et al., the pressure gradient along a curved surface is significant and cannot be neglected in the

analysis, and it is assume that $u = U_w = as$ with $a > 0$, in this context of hybrid nanofluid flow, we assume the fluid is stable, nanoparticle aggregation is negligible, nanoparticles are uniform and spherical, and both the base fluid and nanoparticles are in thermal equilibrium and flow uniformly, leading to governing equations based on these boundary layer approximations Sonika et al.⁽¹⁸⁾.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} ((r + R)\nu) + R \frac{\partial u}{\partial s} = 0 \tag{4}$$

$$\frac{1}{\rho_{thnf}} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} - \frac{u^2}{r + R} = 0 \tag{5}$$

$$\nu \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial s} \frac{Ru}{r + R} + \frac{uv}{r + R} = -\frac{1}{\rho_{thnf}} \frac{R}{r + R} \frac{\partial p}{\partial s} + \nu_{thnf} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \left[\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial^2 r} + \frac{1}{r + R} \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} - \frac{u^2}{(r + R)^2} \right] - \frac{\sigma_{thnf}}{\rho_{thnf}} B_0^2 (u - u_e) - \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \nu_{thnf} (u - u_e) - \frac{F}{\rho_{thnf}} (u^2 - u_e^2) \tag{6}$$

$$\nu \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial T}{\partial s} \frac{Ru}{r + R} = \alpha_{thnf} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial^2 r} + \frac{1}{r + R} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) \tag{7}$$

In this context, v and u denote the velocity components attached in the r and s directions, respectively. T represents the temperature, and the strain of the nanofluid is indicated as well. Moreover α_{thnf} , ρ_{thnf} , σ_{thnf} and ν_{thnf} are the thermal diffusivity, density, electric conductivity and kinematic viscosity of nanofluids. Applied models for thermophysical characteristics of ternary hybrid nanofluid Sunder et al.⁽¹⁹⁾.

Property	Ternary hybrid nanofluid
Density	$\frac{\rho_{thnf}}{\rho_f} = (1 - \phi_1) \left[(1 - \phi_2) \left((1 - \phi_3) + \frac{\phi_3 \rho_3}{\rho_f} \right) + \frac{\phi_2 \rho_2}{\rho_f} \right] + \frac{\phi_1 \rho_1}{\rho_f}$
Heat Capacity	$\frac{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f} = (1 - \phi_1) \left[(1 - \phi_2) \left((1 - \phi_3) + \frac{\phi_3 \rho_3}{(\rho C_p)_f} \right) + \frac{\phi_2 \rho_2}{(\rho C_p)_f} \right] + \frac{\phi_1 \rho_1}{(\rho C_p)_f}$
Dynamic Viscosity	$\mu_{thnf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1 - \phi_1)^{2.5} (1 - \phi_2)^{2.5} (1 - \phi_3)^{2.5}}$
Thermal Conductivity	$\frac{k_{thnf}}{k_f} = \frac{k_1 + 2k_{thnf} + 2\phi_1(k_{thnf} - k_1)}{k_1 + 2k_f + 2\phi_1(k_f - k_1)}$
Electrical Conductivity	$\frac{\sigma_{thnf}}{\sigma} = \frac{\sigma_1(1 + 2\phi_1) - \phi_{thnf}(1 - 2\phi_1)}{\sigma_1(1 - \phi_1) + \sigma_{thnf}(1 + \phi_1)}$

The boundary conditions associated with equations (4) through (7) are presented below.

$$v = v_w, = -\sqrt{av_f S}, u = 0, T = T_w, \text{ at } r = 0, \tag{8}$$

$$u \rightarrow u_e(s) = as, \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \rightarrow 0, T = T_\infty, \text{ as } r \rightarrow \infty,$$

In this context, the variable 'a' represents a positive constant, Introducing the similarity variable are

$$u = u_e f'(\eta), \quad v = \frac{-R}{r + R} \sqrt{\frac{u_f u_e}{s}} f(\eta), \quad \eta = \sqrt{\frac{u_e}{sv_f}} r = \sqrt{\frac{a}{v_f}} r, \tag{9}$$

$$p = \rho u_e^2 P(\eta), \quad \theta(\eta) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty}$$

By utilizing similarity variables **equation (9)**, **equation (4)** is identically satisfied, while **equations (5)** through **(7)** and the corresponding boundary conditions in **equation (8)** are simplified.

$$\frac{\rho_f}{\rho_{thnf}} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \eta} = \frac{1}{\eta + K} f'^2, \tag{10}$$

$$\frac{2k}{\eta + K} \cdot P = \frac{K}{\eta + K} f f'' - \frac{K}{\eta + K} f'^2 + \frac{K}{(\eta + K)^2} f f' + \frac{\nu_{thnf}}{\nu_f} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \left[f''' + \frac{f''}{\eta + K} - \frac{f'}{(\eta + K)^2} \right] \tag{11}$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{thnf}}{\sigma_f} \frac{\rho_f}{\rho_{thnf}} M (f' - 1) - \frac{\nu_{thnf}}{\nu_f} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) A (f' - 1) - \frac{Fr}{\rho_{thnf}} (f'^2 - 1)$$

$$\frac{k_{thnf}}{k_f} \frac{(\rho C_p)_f}{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}} \frac{1}{Pr} \left(\theta'' + \frac{1}{\eta + K} \theta' \right) \frac{K}{\eta + K} f \theta' = 0 \tag{12}$$

and the isolated condition become

$$\begin{aligned} f(0) &= S, \\ f'(0) &= \frac{b}{a} = \gamma, \\ \theta(0) &= 1, \quad \text{as } \eta \rightarrow 0 \\ f'(\infty) &= 1, \\ \theta(\infty) &= 0, \quad \text{as } \eta \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

The important physical quantities, local Nusselt's number Nu_s and skin friction coefficient C_{fs} are defined as $M = \frac{\sigma_f B_0^2}{\rho_f \alpha}$, $A = \frac{\nu_f}{k \alpha}$, $\gamma = \frac{b}{a}$ where $Fr = \frac{C_b}{\sqrt{k_p}}$, $\beta =$ Casson fluid parameter and α curvature parameter $\sqrt{\frac{a}{\nu_f}}$

Eliminating of pressure from **equations (10) and (11)** gives

$$\frac{\nu_{thnf}}{\nu_f} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \left[f^{iv} + \frac{2f'''}{\eta + K} + \frac{f''}{(\eta + K)^2} + \frac{f'}{(\eta + K)^3} \right]$$

$$- \frac{K}{(\eta + K)^2} f f' + \frac{K}{(\eta + K)^2} + (f f'' - f'^2) + \frac{K}{(\eta + K)} (f f'' - f' f''') \tag{14}$$

$$- \frac{\sigma_{thnf}}{\sigma_f} \frac{\rho_f}{\rho_{thnf}} M \left(f'' + \frac{f' - 1}{\eta + K} \right) - \frac{\nu_{thnf}}{\nu_f} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) A \left(f'' + \frac{f' - 1}{\eta + K} \right) - Fr \left(2f f'' + \frac{f'^2 - 1}{\eta + K} \right) = 0$$

These exits two major physical quantities across the sheet surface, one is skin friction coefficient C_{fs} , and other is Reynolds number $\sqrt{(Re_s)}_{C_{fs}}$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{fs} &= \frac{\tau_{rs}}{\rho u_n^2}, \quad \text{Where } \tau_{rs} = u_{thnf} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial r} - \frac{u}{r + R} \right)_{r=0} \\ &= u_{thnf} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \left[as \sqrt{\frac{a}{\nu_f}} f'' - \frac{bs}{r + R} \right]_{r=0} \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

$$\sqrt{(Re_s)_{C_{fs}}} = \frac{\mu_{thnf}}{2\mu_f} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \left[f'' + \frac{\gamma}{\kappa}\right], \text{ Where } Re_s = \frac{as^2}{\nu_f} = \frac{u_e(s)(s)}{\nu_f} \tag{16}$$

$$Nu_s(Re_s) \frac{-1}{2} (Nu) = \frac{-\kappa_{thnf}}{\kappa_f} \theta'(0) \tag{17}$$

2.1 Numerical Technique: bvp4c solver

The solution of the partial differential **Equation (5)**, **Equation (6)** and **Equation (7)** is obtained by reducing them to nonlinear ordinary differential **equation (12)**, **Equation (13)** and **Equation (14)** and solving these equations using MATLAB’s bvp4c boundary value problem solver. The complexity of the equations is reduced by introducing dimensionless variables, enabling a more straight forward solution. The ordinary differential equations are optimized for numerical solution by simplifying their mathematical structure. The implementation details of the bvp4c solver for current problem will be discussed in the subsequent section. The initial two steps focusing on simplifying the system of ordinary differential equations, resulting in a reduced form consisting of five first order equations. The boundary conditions are implementation in step 1, and step 4 involves completing the program’s implementation.

Step 1: First and foremost, we’ll introduce some components for the paired non- linear ordinary differential equations in **Equation (10)**, **Equation (11)** and **Equation (12)**. Firstly, we introduce our system of equation by new variables.

$$f(0) = y(1), f'(0) = y(2), f''(0) = y(3), f'''(0) = y(4), \theta(0) = y(5), \theta'(0) = y(6) \tag{18}$$

Step 2: Now, in the first order system of equations, we will write these new components as follows: $f' = y(2), f'' = y(3)$

$$\begin{aligned} f^{iv} = & \frac{-2y(4)}{\eta + K} + \frac{y(3)}{(\eta + K)^2} - \frac{y(2)}{(\eta + K)^3} + \frac{1}{v_{thnf}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) \left[\frac{K}{(\eta + K)^2} y(1)y(2) - \frac{K}{(\eta + K)^2} (y(1)y(3)) \right. \\ & \left. - y(2)^2 - \frac{K}{\eta + K} (y(1)y(4) - y(2)y(3)) \right] + \frac{\sigma_{thnf}}{\sigma_f} \frac{\rho_f}{\rho_{thnf}} M \left(y(3) + \frac{y(2) - 1}{\eta + K} \right) \\ & + \frac{v_{thnf}}{v_f} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right) A \left(y(3) + \frac{Y(3) - 1}{\eta + K} \right) + \frac{Fr}{v_{thnf}} \left(2y(2)y(3) + \frac{y(2)^2 - 1}{\eta + K} \right) \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \theta = y(5), \quad \theta' = y(6) \\ \theta'' = & \frac{-y(6)}{\eta + K} - Pr \frac{k_f}{k_{thnf}} \frac{(\rho C_p)_{thnf}}{(\rho C_p)_f} \frac{K}{\eta + K} y(1)y(6) \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Step 3: According to the new component, the boundary conditions are expressed as

$$ya(1) - S, \quad ya(2) - \gamma, \quad ya(6) - 1, \tag{21}$$

$$yb(2) \rightarrow 0, \quad yb(3) \rightarrow 0, \quad yb(5) \rightarrow 0,$$

3 Results and Discussion

The local similar solutions of **Equations (12)**, **Equation (13)** and **Equation (14)** are determined numerically employing the bvp4c method. The scrutinize the influence of different value of magnetic field parameter M, porosity parameter A, Prandtl number Pr, Darcy Forchheimer Fr, Casson fluid parameter β , Stagnation parameter S, velocity ratio parameter θ , nanoparticle

Fig 2. Influence of magnetic field parameter M on velocity profile $f'(\eta)$

Fig 3. Influence of magnetic field parameter M on temperature profile $\theta(\eta)$

Fig 4. Influence of Darcy-Forchheimer parameter Fr on velocity profile $f'(\eta)$

Fig 5. Influence of Darcy-Forchheimer parameter Fr on temperature profile $\theta(\eta)$

Fig 6. Influence of Casson fluid parameter β on velocity profile $f'(\eta)$

Fig 7. Influence of Casson fluid parameter β on temperature profile $\theta(\eta)$

Fig 8. Influence of nanoparticles volume fraction parameter ϕ_1 on velocity profile $f'(\eta)$

Fig 9. Influence of nanoparticles volume fraction parameter ϕ_1 on temperature profile $\theta(\eta)$

Table 1. Thermo physical properties of water and considering nanoparticles Alharbi et al. ⁽²⁰⁾

Base fluid and nanoparticles	ρ (kg/m ³)	K (W/mK)	c_p (J/Kg K)	σ (S/m)
Water (H_2O)	997.1	0.613	4179	0.05
Titanium oxide (TiO_2)	4250	8.5938	686.2	2.38×10^6
Cobalt ferrite ($CoFe_2O_4$)	4907	3.7	700	5.51×10^9
Magnesium oxide (MgO)	3560	4.5	955	1.42×10^{-3}

Table 2. Comparison for skin friction $\sqrt{(Re_s)} C_{fs}$ at $M = A = Fr = 0$

K	Abbas et al. ⁽²¹⁾	Present outcome
5.0	1.15763	1.17610
10.0	1.07349	1.07837
20.0	1.03561	1.03684
30.0	1.02353	1.02408
40.0	1.01759	1.01789
50.0	1.01405	1.01424
100.0	1.00704	1.00708

Fig 10. Influence of Stagnation parameter S on skin friction C_f when $M = 5 \times 10^{-7}$, $Pr = 6.2$

Fig 11. Influence of Stagnation parameter S on Nusselt number Nu when $M = 5 \times 10^{-7}$, $Pr = 6.2$

Fig 12. Influence of velocity ratio parameter λ on skin friction C_f when $M = 5 \times 10^{-7}$, $Pr = 6.2$

Fig 13. Influence of velocity ratio parameter λ on Nusselt number Nu when $M = 5 \times 10^{-7}$, $Pr = 6.2$

volume fraction ϕ_1 velocity ratio parameter λ and dimensionless curvature parameter K . The value of Prandtl number Pr is chosen as $Pr = 6.2$. The numerical results obtained are utilized to illustrate boundary layer profiles of velocity $f'(\eta)$ and temperature $\theta(\eta)$ in the form of figures for various values of the relevant parameters. In this study, the following default numbers are used to do calculations: $M = 0.1$, $A = 0.1$, $\lambda = 0.1$, $K = 0.1$, $Fr = 0.1$, $\beta = 0.1$, $S = 1$, $Pr = 6.2$, $\phi_1 = 0.01$. Figure 2 the magnetic field parameter M affects the velocity distribution $f'(\eta)$. The magnetic parameter M reduces both the velocity and thermal boundary layer thickness. The research showed that the Lorentz force created by the magnetic field, has the capability to reduce speed the surface flow by exerting a drag force. Figure 3 depicts the performance of $\theta(\eta)$ for various magnetic field values. The results indicate that the temperature profile improves significantly as the magnetic fluid parameter M is increased. Due to the influence of the Lorentz force, the fluid is likely to produce extra heat energy. Hence, results of this nature can be obtained. Therefore, the outcome of that type can be found. Figure 4 demonstrates how the velocity profile is influenced by the Forchheimer number, where increasing values of the Forchheimer number lead to a stronger inertial effect, resulting in increased resistance to flow and a subsequent decrease in fluid velocity. Figure 5 shows how the variation in Forchheimer number Fr affects the temperature field. It is noted that the temperature field is enhanced in the presence of larger Forchheimer numbers, as the increased resistive force between fluid particles improves the temperature distribution. Figure 6 illustrates how fluid parameter β alters the fluid velocity $f'(\eta)$. The results show that the yield stress decreases with rising inputs of the Casson fluid parameter β , causing a decrease in the velocity and momentum boundary layer thickness. Figure 7 illustrates how fluid parameter β alters the fluid velocity $f'(\eta)$. We noticed that the yield stress lowers up trends with rising inputs of Casson fluid parameter β , and as an outcome, velocity and momentum boundary layer thickness increase for improved inputs of Casson fluid parameter. Figure 8 illustrates the effect of nanoparticle volume fractions ϕ_1 . The velocity profiles exhibited an upward trend as volume concentration increased. This can be attributed to the increased nanofluid density resulting from higher ϕ_1 values which subsequently smooth fluid flow. Figure 9

illustrates the effect of nanoparticle volume fractions ϕ_1 . The temperature profiles demonstrate an increasing trend with higher volume concentrations. This is correlated to the fact that a decrease in ϕ_1 extended the nanofluid density which in turn creates flow hindrance. Stagnation parameter S on skin friction coefficient $C_{f_s} (Re_s)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is depicted in Figure 10. The surface drag force magnitude exhibits a downward trend to increase the value of stagnation parameters S. This occurs as increasing S flattens the surface resulting in decreased skin friction coefficient $C_{f_s} (Re_s)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. Stagnation parameter S, on Nusselt number $Nu_s (Re_s)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ is depicted in Figure 11 the intensity of the surface drag force exhibits an upward trend with rising values of S. This occurs as increasing S reduces surface flatness, leading to increased Nusselt number $Nu_s (Re_s)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$. Velocity ratio parameter λ on skin friction coefficient $C_{f_s} (Re_s)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is depicted in Figure 12 the surface drag force magnitude exhibits a downward trend with rising values of λ . This is decline in both Skin friction and heat transfer rate. This occurs because the Lorentz force, a drag like force, weakens with increasing velocity ratio parameter λ , injecting additional energy into the boundary layer. Velocity ratio parameter λ on Nusselt number $Nu_s (Re_s)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ Nu is depicted in Figure 13 the intensity of the surface drag force exhibits an upward trend with rising values of λ . Skin friction $C_{f_s} (Re_s)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and heat transfer rate also improves. Because the rise velocity ratio parameter λ , leads to an increase in Lorentz force, introducing more energy into the boundary layer.

The non-linear ordinary differential Eq.(12), Eq.(13) and Eq.(14) are solved numerically using MATLAB's bvp4c algorithm, exploring the effect of different values of magnetic parameter M, Porosity parameter A, Prandtl number Pr, Darcy Forchheimer Fr, Casson fluid parameter β , Stagnation parameter S, Velocity ratio parameter θ , Nanoparticle volume fraction ϕ_1 and curvature parameter in dimensionless form K. The first step in this approach is to convert the fourth order differential equation into a set of first order equations by defining new variables. It is essential that the assumed solution adheres to the boundary conditions outlined in (13) and replicate the expected behavior of the solution. Table 1 shows a comparative analysis of the skin friction coefficient $C_{f_s} (Re_s)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ When $M = 0$, $Fr = 0$ and $A = 0$ with Abbas et al. (19).

4 Conclusions

This article focuses on Significance of Darcy Forchheimer Flow and MHD Stagnation Characteristics of Casson Ternary Nanofluid Flow over Porous Curved Stretching Surface. The mathematical model includes the Darcy-Forchheimer term in the governing equations for velocity and temperature, enabling the investigation of porous media flows. Furthermore, the study examines and compares the skin friction coefficient and Nusselt number to gain insights into the flow and heat transfer characteristics. The Bvp4c solver in MATLAB is utilized to obtain numerical solutions for the nonlinear ordinary differential equations. The main results of this study can be summarized as follows:

- In temperature profile $\theta(\eta)$ boosts for higher values of ϕ_1 M, Fr, β .
- Velocity distributions $f'(\eta)$ rises for increasing values of ϕ_1 and while declines for Fr M and β .
- In case of skin friction $C_{f_s} (Re_s)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ shows decreasing behavior for S and λ whereas Nusselt number $Nu_s (Re_s)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ increases behavior for S and λ .

4.1 Future scope and limitations

Future scope:

This study's findings on Casson ternary nanofluid flow over porous curved surfaces can inform advancements in heat transfer systems and biomedical applications. Further research can explore non-Newtonian fluid behavior in complex geometries.

Limitations:

The study's assumptions (eg. steady-state, incompressible flow) and simplifications may not fully capture real-world complexities. Experimental validation and consideration of additional factors (e.g., turbulence, surface roughness) could enhance accuracy.

Nomenclature

Fr: Darcy Forchheimer

A: Porosity parameter

M: Magnetic field parameter

Pr: Prandtl number

S: Stagnation

K: Curvature parameter

β : Casson fluid parameter

θ : Velocity ratio parameter
 q_m : Wall mass flux ($\text{kgm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$)
 p_y : Yield stress
 λ : Velocity ratio parameter
 T_∞ : Free stream temperature (K)
 T_w : Temperature of sheet (K)
 q_r : Radiative heat flux (W)
 v : Fluid velocity in r -direction (m/s^{-1})
 u : Velocity of the stretching sheet in s - direction (m/s^{-1})
 C_p : Specific heat ($\text{Jkg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)
 C : Concentration (kgm^{-3})
 Re_s : Local Reynolds number
 Nu_s : Local Nusselt number
 C_{fs} : skin friction coefficient
 Nu_s : Local Nusselt number
 a : Positive constant
 P : Dimensionless Pressure
 q_w : Wall heat flux (Wm^{-2})
 T : Temperature of fluid (K)
 (r,s) : Curvilinear coordinates
 (TiO_2) : titanium dioxide
 MgO : magnesium oxide
 $(CoFe_2O_4)$: cobalt ferrite oxide
 R : Radius of curvature
Greek symbols:
 η : Similarity transformation
 ϕ_1 : Nanoparticle volume fraction
 ρ_{thnf} : Density
 α_{thnf} : Thermal diffusivity
 σ_{thnf} : Electric conductivity
 ν_{thnf} : Kinematic viscosity
 π : Deformation rate component
 π_c : Critical product value
 μ_B : Plastic dynamic viscosity
 ρc_p : Heat capacity
 τ_{rs} : Shear wall stress (Nm^{-2})

References

- 1) Dinesh PA, Sumithra R, Roopa KR, Yadav S, Kumar KA, Archana MA, et al. Numerical Investigation on Forchheimer MHD Non-Newtonian Fluid over an Exponential Stretching Sheet with Joule and Viscous Dissipation. *Journal of Mines, Metals and Fuels*. 2023;p. 49–57. <https://doi.org/10.18311/jmmf/2024/47260>.
- 2) Jat K, Sharma K, Choudhary P, Soni P, Ali R, Ganesh M. Significance of Darcy–Forchheimer Casson fluid flow past a non-permeable curved stretching sheet with the impacts of heat and mass transfer. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*. 2024 09;61:104907. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2024.104907>.
- 3) Abbas MS, Shaheen A, Abbas N, Shatanawi W. Dynamic analysis of radiative chemical species with non-Newtonian fluid flow over an exponentially curved stretching sheet. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part E: Journal of Process Mechanical Engineering*. 2024 09.
- 4) Vidhya KG, Nagaraja B, Almeida F, Kumar P. Numerical exploration of micropolar fluid stratified flow over curved stretching sheet under buoyancy effect. *ZAMM-Journal of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics/Zeitschrift für Angewandte Mathematik und Mechanik*. 2024 12;104(12).
- 5) Nagaraja B, Gireesha BJ, Almeida F, Kumar P, Ajaykumar AR. Entropy analysis of Darcy-Forchheimer model of Prandtl nanofluid over a curved stretching sheet and heat transfer optimization by ANOVA-Taguchi technique. *Journal of Applied and Computational Mechanics*. 2024 04;10(2):287–303. <https://doi.org/10.22055/jacm.2023.44524.4229>.
- 6) Kumar P, Nagaraja B, AR A, Almeida F. Optimization design based on Taguchi method and statistical analysis of variance for thermo-diffusive flow over a curved sheet: entropy analysis. *International Journal of Modelling and Simulation*. 2024 12;p. 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02286203.2024.2437829>.
- 7) Manjunatha S, Puneeth V, Gireesha BJ, Chamkha A. Theoretical study of convective heat transfer in ternary nanofluid flowing past a stretching sheet. *Journal of Applied and Computational Mechanics*. 2022 10;8(4):1279–1286. <https://doi.org/10.22055/jacm.2021.37698.3067>.

- 8) Singh B, Sood S, Thakur A, Chandel S. Numerical analysis of mixed convection and Thomson-Troian slip effects on ternary nanofluid flow and heat transfer over a stretching sheet with porous media: Darcy-Forchheimer model. *Applied and Computational Mechanics*. 2024 12;18(2). <https://doi.org/10.24132/acm.2024.894>.
- 9) Arif M, Kumam P, Kumam W, Mostafa Z. Heat transfer analysis of radiator using different shaped nanoparticles water-based ternary hybrid nanofluid with applications: A fractional model. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*. 2022 03;31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2022.101837>.
- 10) Ali B, Jubair S. Rheological properties of Darcy–Forchheimer hybrid nanofluid flow with thermal emission and heat source over a curved slippery surface. *Pramana*. 2023 08;97(3).
- 11) Singh B, Sood S. Hybrid nanofluids preparation, thermo-physical properties, and applications: A Review. *Hybrid Advances*. 2024 04.
- 12) Aljuaydi F, Khan Z, Islam S. Numerical investigations of ion slip and Hall effects on Cattaneo-Christov heat and mass fluxes in Darcy-Forchheimer flow of Casson fluid within a porous medium, utilizing non-Fourier double diffusion theories through artificial neural networks ANNs. *International Journal of Thermofluids*. 2023 11;20.
- 13) Almeida F, Kumar P, Ajaykumar AR, Nagaraja B. Implementation of artificial neural network using Levenberg Marquardt algorithm for Casson–Carreau nanofluid flow over exponentially stretching curved surface. *Neural Computing and Applications*. 2024 11;36(31):19393–19415. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-024-10193-3>.
- 14) Mahabaleshwar US, Maranna T, Mishra M, Hatami M, Sunden B. Radiation effect on stagnation point flow of Casson nanofluid past a stretching plate/cylinder. *Scientific Reports*. 2024 01;14(1).
- 15) Wang J, Xu YP, Qahiti R, Jafaryar M, Alazwari MA, Abu-Hamdeh NH, et al. Simulation of hybrid nanofluid flow within a microchannel heat sink considering porous media analyzing CPU stability. *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*. 2022 01;208.
- 16) Rehman KU, Shatanawi W, Al-Mdallal QM. A comparative remark on heat transfer in thermally stratified MHD Jeffrey fluid flow with thermal radiations subject to cylindrical/plane surfaces. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*. 2022;32.
- 17) Vyas P, Gajanand, Khan S. Irreversibility analysis for Casson thermo-fluidics inside a cone: Cattaneo–Christov heat flux. *Heat Transfer*. 2022 07;51(5):4584–4619. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hjt.22514>.
- 18) Sharma S. Study on Darcy-Forchheimer Flow and MHD Boundary Layer Flow with Heat Transfer Characteristics of Williamson Nanofluid Over Curved Stretching Surface. In: *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*;vol. 1979. 2021.
- 19) Sundar LS, Mouli KVC, Said Z, Sousa AC. Heat transfer and second law analysis of ethylene glycol-based ternary hybrid nanofluid under laminar flow. *Journal of Thermal Science and Engineering Applications*. 2021 10;13(5).
- 20) Alharbi KA, Ahmed AE, Sidi MO, Ahammad NA, Mohamed A, El-Shorbagy MA, et al. Computational valuation of Darcy ternary-hybrid nanofluid flow across an extending cylinder with induction effects. *Micromachines*. 2022 04;13(4).
- 21) Abbas N, Rehman KU, Shatanawi W, Malik MY. Numerical study of heat transfer in hybrid nanofluid flow over permeable nonlinear stretching curved surface with thermal slip. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*. 2022 06;135.